

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF QUERCETIN ACTING AS ANTI-AGING TREATMENT

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DECLARATION OF RESEARCH SCHOLARS

We hereby declare that the work described in this project report, titled ‘Molecular docking studies of Quercetin acting as an anti-aging treatment’ which is being submitted by us in partial fulfilment of the requirements for SI. B. Pharmacy, Semester-8 at the Faculty of Pharmacy, Marwadi University, Gujarat, India. It is the result of investigations carried out by us under the guidance of Ms Palak K Vadodariya, Assistant Professor, Faculty of Pharmacy, Marwadi University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India.

The work is original and has not been submitted for any Degree/Diploma of this or any other university.

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ABSTRACT

The course of aging is a complicated, multipronged process, during which the quality of functioning drastically declines, ultimately becoming the leading cause of age-related ailments. Quercetin, a well-known polyphenolic component that can be found in fruits and vegetables, has lately under studies showed its anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer capabilities. The disclosure of the molecular structure at back of anti-aging effect of quercetin will rekindle the development of new therapies. Polyphenols exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-glycation activities, which contribute to their ability to mitigate age-related cellular damage and promote longevity. Furthermore, polyphenols modulate signaling pathways involved in cellular senescence, apoptosis, and DNA repair, highlighting their multifaceted roles in aging processes. This review explores the current understanding of polyphenols as anti-aging compounds, focusing on the receptors involved, mechanisms of action and chemical constituents. This study aims to elucidate the mechanisms through which polyphenols exert their anti-aging effects, employing molecular docking simulations to analyze their interactions with key molecular targets involved in aging processes such as oxidative stress, inflammation, and cellular senescence. With molecular docking simulations in this study, the objective is to show the mechanism of quercetin binding to the proteins that are associated with mechanisms of aging, including sirtuins (SIRT1 and SIRT6), and AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) and Nrf2. The crystal structures of these proteins are from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) and software including Auto Dock Vina and Pymol for visualization. The study resulted in an affection between quercetin and all proteins with binding free energies between -5.0 and -9.0 kcal/mol. Quercetin form hydrogen and hydrophobic interaction with the key amino acids in the catalytic domains of SIRT1 and SIRT6 by which enzymatic activity is performed. However, further research is warranted to elucidate the specific polyphenolic compounds that confer optimal anti-aging benefits and to translate these findings into clinical interventions for promoting healthy aging.

Keywords: Quercetin; Anti-aging; Polyphenols; Antioxidant; Docking; Sirtuins

1. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1.1. Aim of the study:

Molecular docking studies of Quercetin acting as Anti-aging Treatment.

1.2. Objectives of the study:

1. To conduct a comprehensive literature review on anti-aging.
2. To prepare protein and ligands using suitable software for effective docking.
3. To perform molecular docking studies to investigate the binding affinity of different polyphenols.
4. To analyze the results of the docking studies to identify polyphenols with the highest binding affinity to the target receptor (3M89).
5. To conduct ADMET analysis to filter out ligands with poor pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics properties and high toxicity.

2. INTRODUCTION

Aging remains among unsolved problems of modern dermatology with unmet as yet therapeutic needs⁽¹⁾. Aging is defined as a cumulative loss of homeostasis, self-repair, rejuvenation, performance, and fitness in various tissues over time⁽²⁾. Skin aging is a complex biological process driven by a variety of intrinsic and external variables. Wrinkles, uneven tone, loss of suppleness, and thinning are common signs of aging skin. Skin health is considered one of the major aspects representing total well-being and the perception of health in humans; thus, anti-aging treatments to counteract aging symptoms and dysfunction have been developed over the last decades⁽³⁾. The process of biological aging is driven by a series of interrelated mechanisms through different signal pathways, including oxidative stress, inflammatory states, autophagy and others. In addition, the intestinal microbiota plays a key role in regulating oxidative stress of microglia, maintaining homeostasis of microglia and alleviating age-related diseases. Tea polyphenols can effectively regulate the composition of the intestinal microbiota⁽⁴⁾. Intracellular and extracellular oxidative stress initiated by reactive oxygen species (ROS) advance skin aging, which is characterized by wrinkles and atypical pigmentation. Because UV enhances ROS generation in cells, skin aging is usually discussed in relation to UV exposure⁽⁵⁾. Solar broadband UV irradiation is commonly regarded as a major causative reason for cutaneous photoaging⁽⁶⁾.

It is believed that postponing ageing is more effective and less expensive than the treatment of particular age-related diseases⁽⁷⁾. Nine hallmarks have been identified based on their alteration during aging and their capacity to increase longevity. The pathways and the molecular mechanisms to improve lifespan and health span are controlled by behavioral, pharmacologic and dietary factors, which remain largely unknown. Among them, naturally occurring compounds, such as polyphenols, are considered potential anti-aging agents, because of their ability to modulate some of the evolutionarily conserved hallmarks of aging, including oxidative damage, inflammation, cell senescence, and autophagy⁽⁸⁾. Polyphenolic extracts are highlighted because they have proven antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, antimicrobial, and supporting activity in solar photo protection⁽⁹⁾. The use of antioxidants is an effective approach to prevent symptoms related to photo-induced aging of the skin⁽¹⁰⁾.

Quercetin is among the widely occurring polyphenol, found abundantly in nature⁽¹¹⁾. “Quercetum”, the Latin term for the flavonoid quercetin means oak forest and a compound that is yellow colored compound. This belongs to the class flavonol and is not synthesized in the human body. It is commonly present in different plant products⁽¹²⁾. This compound is easy to dissolve in lipids and alcohol, is insoluble in cold water, and has poor solubility in hot water. Quercetin is most commonly found in large quantities in different fruits and vegetables which include apple, berries, cherries, red leaf lettuce, onions, asparagus, and in small quantities in pepper, broccoli, peas, and tomatoes⁽¹³⁾. Onion is known to have the highest quantity of quercetin. This plant compound is possessed antioxidant properties and is considered to have a protective function against aging⁽¹⁴⁾. Quercetin is a potent molecule that can be used to cure various health-related issues. Quercetin manifests antioxidant properties both in vivo and in vitro^(15; 16). Free radical scavenging activity of quercetin protects from various age-associated disorders⁽¹⁷⁾. Quercetin is a large class of flavonoids, consisting of five classes of hydroxyl

groups, 3,5,7,3', and 4' of the basic flavonol skeleton. The chemical formula for quercetin is C₁₅H₁₀O₇. The structure shares a common flavone nucleus made up of two benzene rings and is connected by a heterocyclic pyrone ring⁽¹⁸⁾. This is also known to have a protective function against aging. Some of these classes of hydroxyls are glycosylated to different quercetin glycosides and form the major quercetin derivatives. It is noteworthy that several studies have shown the relationship between the structural activities of quercetin and its derivatives on antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities⁽¹⁹⁾. They found that the modification of quercetin reduces its antioxidant activity, and the total activity was found to be as follows: quercetin > tamarixetin = isorhamnetin > quercetin-3-O-glucuronide > isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside > quercetin-3,5,7,3',4'-pentamethylether > quercetin-3,4'-di-glucoside, indicating that the 3-hydroxyl quercetin group plays a significant role in antioxidant activity⁽²⁰⁾. Moreover, it is reported that methylated quercetin metabolites (e.g., isorhamnetin and tamarixetin) showed higher antioxidant activity than quercetin by inhibiting lipid peroxidation⁽²¹⁾. Quercetin exerts neuroprotective effects against chronic aging-related diseases via targeting SIRT1 to regulate cellular senescence and multiple aging-related cellular processes such as SIRT1/Keap1/Nrf2/HO-1 and PI3K/Akt/GSK-3 β mediated oxidative stress, SIRT1/NF- κ B mediated inflammatory response, SIRT1/PGC1 α /eIF2 α /ATF4/CHOP mediated mitochondrial damage, and SIRT1/FoxO mediated autophagy⁽²²⁾. Quercetin also reduces the overproduction of ROS, damage caused by trauma, improves TNF- α , and prevents myocardial cell injury caused by Ca²⁺ overload. Quercetin can thus effectively prevent injury caused by oxidative stress⁽²³⁾. Below is a diagram of structure of quercetin:

Figure 1: Structure of Quercetin

3. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Molecular docking studies of Quercetin as an anti-aging medication aim to determine how this natural flavonoid interacts with specific proteins implicated in the aging process. Quercetin is renowned for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and possible senolytic properties, which can help fight aging at the cellular level. This research aim to determine how quercetin binds to 6m89 and influences the activity of aging-related molecules and processes, such as oxidative stress regulators, DNA repair enzymes, and inflammatory mediators. By modeling quercetin's molecular interactions, researchers want to identify its mechanisms of action, improve its effectiveness and specificity through structural alterations, and investigate its potential as a foundation for generating new anti-aging medicines. This computational technique is critical for furthering our understanding of quercetin's significance in aging and for the design of more effective anti-aging interventions.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

4.1 Receptors involved in aging process

Aging involves various biological processes, and while there isn't a single receptor solely responsible for aging, several receptors and signaling pathways play crucial roles ⁽²⁴⁾. Some key receptors and pathways involved in aging include:

1. Nuclear receptors:

Nuclear receptors, such as peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) and estrogen receptors, play roles in aging-related processes such as inflammation, metabolism, and cellular senescence ⁽²⁵⁾.

➤ *1a. Vitamin D receptor (VDRs).*

The ligand for VDRs is the active form of vitamin D calcitriol (1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol). The most common disorders associated with aging and VDR/calcitriol deficiency are sarcopenia (a degenerative loss of skeletal muscle mass), and osteoporosis ⁽²⁶⁾.

➤ *1b. Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs).*

Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) are key regulators in various age-associated pathophysiological processes related to energy metabolism and oxidative stress. A progressive rise of oxidative stress and related inflammatory reaction appears the hallmarks of the aging process and many age-related diseases. PPARs are important redox-sensitive transcription factors and their dysregulated activations seem to be major culprits for these pathological processes. PPARs are nuclear transcription factors that play a key role in energy homeostasis and in the pathophysiology of many age-related disorders, such as increased oxidative stress, inflammatory reactions, and insulin resistance, and PPAR agonists can be used in the treatment of these disorders ⁽²⁷⁾. Energy restriction, the most effective intervention in offsetting the effects of aging, leads to declines in oxidative stress and a lessening in inflammatory reaction, reduced adipose tissue and fasting glycemia levels, and thus prolonging life ⁽²⁸⁾.

2. Transmembrane receptors (metabotropic, G-protein coupled):

➤ 2a. Dopamine D1 receptors

Dopamine influences skeletal muscle tone through the activation of type D1 receptors on somatic motoneurons ⁽²⁹⁾. Aging negatively affects dopamine transporters and receptors, but not on production of dopamine ⁽³⁰⁾.

3. Insulin/IGF-1 Signaling:

Insulin and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) receptors regulate metabolism, growth, and longevity. Dysregulation of this pathway is implicated in aging-related diseases like diabetes and neurodegenerative disorders ⁽³¹⁾.

4. mTOR (Target of Rapamycin):

TOR is a nutrient-sensing pathway that regulates cell growth and metabolism. Inhibition of TOR signaling has been shown to extend lifespan in various organisms ⁽³²⁾. mTOR is encoded by a single gene and its protein product is a component of two distinct complexes—mTOR complex 1 (mTORC1) and 2 (mTORC2) ³—which differ functionally and structurally and in their sensitivity to rapamycin ⁽³³⁾⁽³⁴⁾⁽³⁵⁾. mTORC1 responds to a plethora of extracellular stimuli and intracellular cues, such as amino acids, hormones, growth factors, energetic stress, and oxygen. These factors initiate mTOR-dependent anabolic processes, including nucleotide, lipid, and protein synthesis while inhibiting autophagy, which results in stimulation of cellular growth and proliferation ⁽³⁶⁾.

5. AMP-activated Protein Kinase (AMPK):

AMPK is a cellular energy sensor that regulates metabolism and cellular stress responses. Activation of AMPK can promote longevity by enhancing cellular homeostasis ⁽³⁷⁾.

6. Sirtuins:

Sirtuins are a family of proteins involved in regulating cellular processes such as DNA repair, metabolism, and stress response. SIRT3 is the only sirtuin for which evidence exists that it can influence longevity in humans. It was shown that a certain polymorphism in SIRT3 gene can be found more often in long-lived people ⁽³⁸⁾. Activation of sirtuins has been linked to increased lifespan in various organisms ⁽³⁹⁾. Sirtuins have long been recognized as regulators of ageing, and overexpression of some sirtuins has been shown to extend lifespan in several organisms.

The suppression of cellular senescence by sirtuin is mainly mediated through delaying the age-related telomere attrition, sustaining genome integrity and promoting DNA damage repair ⁽⁴⁰⁾.

7. *Nrf2 (Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2):*

Nrf2 is a transcription factor that regulates the expression of antioxidant and detoxification enzymes. Activation of Nrf2 signaling can mitigate oxidative stress and promote longevity ⁽⁴¹⁾.

8. *FOXO (Forkhead box O) Transcription Factors:*

FOXO proteins are key regulators of longevity and stress resistance. They regulate the expression of genes involved in cell cycle arrest, apoptosis, and DNA repair ⁽⁴²⁾.

9. *Telomerase:*

Telomerase is an enzyme that maintains the length of telomeres, which are protective caps at the ends of chromosomes. Longer telomeres are associated with cellular longevity and reduced cellular senescence. Telomerase activity declines with age but can be modulated to potentially slow down aging processes ^(43; 44).

10. *Heat Shock Proteins (HSPs):*

HSPs are a group of proteins that help protect cells from stressors such as heat, oxidative stress, and inflammation. They assist in protein folding, repair damaged proteins, and promote cellular survival under stress conditions, thereby contributing to anti-aging mechanisms ⁽⁴⁵⁾.

11. *NAD+ (Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide):*

NAD⁺ is a coenzyme involved in cellular energy production and various metabolic processes. Increasing NAD⁺ levels, often achieved through supplementation with precursors like nicotinamide riboside (NR) or nicotinamide mononucleotide (NMN), has been linked to improved mitochondrial function, DNA repair, and longevity ⁽⁴⁶⁾. During ageing, NAD⁺ levels decline, and many enzymes associated with NAD⁺ degradation and biosynthesis are altered. Additionally, this decline in NAD⁺ levels during ageing has been linked to the development and progression of ageing-related diseases, including atherosclerosis, arthritis, hypertension, cognitive decline, diabetes and cancer. During ageing, cells exposed to metabolic, genotoxic or oncogene-induced stress undergo essentially irreversible cell cycle arrest known as cellular senescence ⁽⁴⁷⁾. One major phenotype of senescent cells and how they are thought to promote disease is the increased expression of inflammatory mediators, mostly cytokines and

chemokines, known as the senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP), which contributes to impaired tissue homeostasis by interfering with stem cell regeneration, tissue and wound repair and inflammaging⁽⁴⁸⁾ (49).

Figure 2: Role of SIRT1 in improvement of the attenuation effect of quercetin on of aging-induced disorders⁽⁵⁰⁾.

4.2 Characterization of PDB-ID:

Suitable PDB-ID was selected from Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) Protein Data Bank (PDB) an online database (<https://www.rcsb.org>). Criteria for selection used was:

Suitable PDB-ID was found to be 6M89. Details of the protein 6m89 is shown below;

Table 1; Characterization of PDBID.

PDB-ID	6M89
NAME	Crystal structure of the core catalytic domain of human inositol phosphate multikinase in complex with Quercetin.
CLASSIFICATION	TRANSFERASE/TRANSFERASE Inhibitor
MUTATION	NO
RESOLUTION	1.85 Å
RELEASE DATE	2019-01-23

Figure 3. 3D structure of protein:6m89

4.3 Preparation of ligand file

❖ *Chemical structures of polyphenols possessing antiaging properties*

quercetin

Caffeic acid

Genistein

Rosmarinic acid

(-)-Epicatechin

Chicoric acid

Fisetin

Tyrosol

Curcumin

Cycloastrogenol

EGCG

Resveratrol

Sappanone

Myricetin

Procyanidin

Tambulin

Figure 4: The chemical structures of polyphenols possessing anti-aging properties.

5. METHODOLOGY

The foundation of this research is the identification and optimization of Quercetin and other polyphenols as antiaging treatment through the use of computational and data science tools and methodologies, expanded upon earlier literature reports. A ligand file of different compounds was created, and their activities were examined *in silico* through the use of molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations. Quercetin was utilized as a template to compare the binding activity and stability of the other polyphenols in order to accomplish our goal of repurposing pharmaceuticals.

An outline of the approach is provided below:

5.1 Data set preparation

➤ Tools for Preparation

- *Auto Dock Tools (ADT):*

Useful for preparing both ligand and receptor files, including adding hydrogens, assigning charges, and converting to PDBQT format.

- *PyMOL:*

While primarily a visualization tool, PyMOL can be used to clean protein structures, remove water, and more.

- *MGLTools:*

Includes AutoDockTools (ADT), which is specifically designed for preparing molecules for docking with AutoDock. It can add hydrogens, calculate Gasteiger charges, and more. It directly supports the preparation of pdbqt files for AutoDock and AutoDock Vina.

Crystal structure of the core catalytic domain of human inositol phosphate multikinase in complex with quercetin (PDB ID: 6M89) was selected for molecular docking study based on literature review (Yang et al. 2021) crystal structure of these proteins has been collected from the Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) Protein Data Bank (PDB) an online database (<https://www.rcsb.org>). Preprocessing, optimization and minimization processes were done by using PyMOL. This process is included in Schrodinger suit-maestro (v11.1). The structures were optimized at pH 7.0, water molecules fewer than 3 H-bonds to non-waters were removed and polar hydrogen. Restrained minimization was done where heavy atoms are converged to RMSD of 0.30 Å on the implemented OPLS3 force field.

5.2 Pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic analysis

In general, the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics properties may have a potential effect on the drug-likeness of derived compounds⁽⁵¹⁾. Thus, in our study, the evaluation of the molecular properties of the compounds was accomplished using online ADMET tools such as swissADME⁽⁵²⁾. The SwissADME Web tool enables the computation of key physicochemical, pharmacokinetic, drug-like and related parameters for one or multiple molecules.

SwissADME web tool that gives free access to a pool of fast yet robust predictive models for physicochemical properties, pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness, among which in-house proficient methods such as the BOILED-Egg, iLOGP and Bioavailability Radar.

The above mentioned servers estimates the ADMET properties based on fundamental rules such as Lipinski's rule of five (Ro5), Vebers rule, Ghose rules and so on. For instance, the rule of five, attempts to quantify the molecules on the basis of molecular weight ≤ 500 Da, $\log P \leq 5$, hydrogen bond donors ≤ 5 , hydrogen bond acceptors ≤ 10 , and van der Waals polar surface area (PSA) $\leq 140 \text{ \AA}^2$.³⁸ All these Ro5 parameters were explored by Swiss-ADME tool and the percentage of human intestinal absorption together with TPSA were calculated by pkCSM tool. Additionally, influential descriptors such as blood–brain barrier (BBB), cytochrome (CYP450 substrates and inhibitors) and toxicity were also explored for all the compounds using admetSAR. Altogether, these parameters are of immense importance to predict the drug-likeness properties of the ligand molecules.

5.3 Molecular docking

Auto Dock Vina is a suite of computerized docking devices like Auto Dock. It is intended to predict how little atoms, for example, substrates or drug candidates, bind to a receptor of known 3D structure. Auto Dock really comprises of two principle programs: Auto Dock plays out the docking of the ligand to a lot of grids describing the target protein, Auto Grid pre-computes these grids. In addition to using them for docking, the nuclear liking grids can be imagined. This can help, for instance, to direct natural manufactured scientific expert's configuration better fasteners. A graphical UI called ADT (Auto dock Tools) has been utilized sets up which bonds that will treat as rotatable in the ligand. This empowers to investigate the docking association between the medication (ligand) and the medication target (receptor) in silico. The Auto dock apparatus has been utilized for contemplating the connection among polyphenols and Anti- aging .

5.3.1 Preparing the Protein:

Protein Data Bank (PDB) documents can have an assortment of potential issues that should be revised before they can be utilized in AutoDock. These potential issues incorporate missing atoms, included waters, more than one atom, chain breaks, alternate locations etc. The water particles must be expelled and polar hydrogen atoms must be included and spare in "pdb" format. The receptor document utilized via AutoDockVina must be in "pdbqt" design which is pdb in addition to 'q' charge and 't' AutoDock molecule types which recognizes the distinctive kinds of atoms.

5.3.2 Preparing the Ligand:

Before docking partial nuclear charges are connected to every particle of the ligand and distinguish between aliphatic and aromatic carbons: names for aromatic carbons start with 'A' rather than 'C'. AutoDock ligands are written in records with unique keywords perceived via AutoDock. The root is an inflexible arrangement of particles, while the branches are rotatable gatherings of molecules associated with the unbending root. The root is identified utilizing

Detect Root alternative under Torsions. The chose torsions are connected to the ligand. After all the above conditions are set the ligand is spared in "pdbqt" group.

5.3.3 Preparing the Configuration File:

The design record tells AutoDock Vina which has the details need by the Vina to run docking investigation, for example, the information document names, grid box parameters which gives the details of the search space: by adjusting the directions of the matrix put away bring the receptor and ligand into the grid area, yield of the docked postures, thoroughness, number of modes to be created in a typical content.

5.3.4 Identification of active site of the receptor

An active site is a specific place on the surface of the receptor where the compounds tend to bind and causes conformational changes to induce a pharmacological action . The active site determination is an integral part of docking simulation because it specifies the binding site of a ligand on the receptor.

5.3.5 Running AutoDock Vina Program:

AutoDock Vina is executed utilizing order brief in Windows. Browse through the area of the receptor and the ligand records in pdbqt design. The areas are determined in the vina.exe file followed by the design document name.

5.3.6 Scoring and Ranking:

Based on binding energy, interaction patterns, and other variables, rate and order the docked positions.

We identified the ligands that bind and interact with the target protein in the most advantageous ways.

5.3.7 Analysis:

A comparison with known experimental data was made in order to validate the docking results. Target protein active site residues are analyzed for binding modes and interactions of top-ranked ligands. Important interactions that determine binding affinity and selectivity are then identified.

We were able to identify lead compounds with the highest promising binding affinities and interactions based on the docking results.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 ADME assessment

The ADME properties were explored in the initial stage of screening using online Swiss ADME to eliminate false positive predictions. For instance, properties like molecular weight, TPSA, hydrogen bond acceptor and hydrogen bond donor were found. Molecular weights of all the ligands were found to be below 500g/mol. Further, most of the designed ligands and reference exhibited appropriate TPSA (<140Å²), hydrogen bond donor and log P value. Notably all the ligands obeyed Lipinski rule of five. The results are shown in the tables below;

Table 2: Insilico ADMET screening for proposed compounds.

Molecule	Formula	MW	#Rotatable bonds	#H-bond acceptors	#H-bond donors	MR	TPSA	iLOGP	Lipinski #violations
1	C15H10O7	302.24	1	7	5	78.03	131.36	1.63	0
2	C9H8O4	180.16	2	4	3	47.16	77.76	0.97	0
3	C15H10O5	270.24	1	5	3	73.99	90.9	1.91	0
4	C15H14O6	290.27	1	6	5	74.33	110.38	1.47	0
5	C18H16O8	360.31	7	8	5	91.4	144.52	1.17	0
6	C30H50O5	490.72	2	5	4	138.15	90.15	4.02	0
7	C15H10O6	286.24	1	6	4	76.01	111.13	1.5	0
8	C8H10O2	138.16	2	2	2	39.4	40.46	1.4	0
9	C14H12O3	228.24	2	3	3	67.88	60.69	1.71	0
10	C16H12O5	284.26	1	5	3	76.7	86.99	1.74	0
11	C21H20O6	368.38	8	6	2	102.8	93.06	3.27	0
12	C22H18O11	458.37	4	7	8	112.06	197.37	1.87	0
13	C15H10O8	318.24	1	8	6	80.06	151.59	1.08	1
14	C18H16O7	344.32	4	7	2	91.44	98.36	3.11	0
15	C15H10O5	270.52	0	5	3	70.78	94.83	1.8	0
recommended values		>500	<10	<10	<5	40-130	20-140	<5	

Table 3: Insilico ADMET screening for proposed compounds.

Molecule	GI absorption	BBB permeability	Ghose #violations	Veber #violations	Bioavailability Score	Synthetic Accessibility
1	High	No	0	0	0.55	3.23
2	High	No	0	0	0.56	1.81
3	High	No	0	0	0.55	2.87
4	High	No	0	0	0.55	3.5
5	Low	No	0	1	0.56	3.38
6	High	No	3	0	0.55	7.28
7	High	No	0	0	0.55	3.16
8	High	Yes	2	0	0.55	1
9	High	Yes	0	0	0.55	2.02
10	High	No	0	0	0.55	2.93
11	High	No	0	0	0.55	2.97
12	Low	No	0	1	0.17	4.2
13	Low	No	0	1	0.55	3.27
14	High	No	0	0	0.55	3.51
15	High	No	0	0	0.55	2.57

6.2 Molecular docking results

Table 4: Molecular docking results

Molecule	Best_Energy(kcal/mol)	Interaction
Quercetin(cocrystal ligand)	-7.5	ASP A: 385, VAL A:73, ASP A:144 , LEU A: 254, VAL A: 133, ASP A: 132, ILE A: 384, ILE A:65
Caffeic acid	-6.6	LYS A:146, GLN A:164,ALA A:250, GLN

		A: 78, ALA A: 387, GLU A:86, ASP A:385
Genistein	-7.2	LYS A:75, LEU A:130, PRO A:111, ILE A:384, GLU A:86, ASP A:385, TYR A:90, VAL A:73
Rosmaric acid	-6.3	ILE A:65, ASP A:144, LEU A:254, VAL A:133, VAL A:73, ASP A:132
Epicatechin	-6.4	LYS A:108, LYS A:235, LYS A:232, VAL A:381
Chicoric acid	-6.4	ARG A:200, GLU A:159, VAL A:381, LYS A:235
Fisetin	-7.6	GLN A:163, ARG A:107, ALA A:96, LEU A:87, GLY A:115, TYR A:114, TYR A:113, LYS A:112
Tyrosol	-6.6	LEU A:126, ASNA:124, LEU A:77, PRO A:79, PRO A:80, PRO A: 84
Curcumin	-6.1	ASP A:144, ILE A:179, ASP A:13, LEU A:254, PRO A:111, ASP A:132
Cycloastrogenol	-7.1	GLN A:196, MET A 181, ASP A: 144, ILE A:142, ARG A:182, LEU A: 254, ILE A: 65, VAL A: 133
EGCG	-6.8	LYS A:146, GLN A:164, ALA A:250, GLN A:78, ALA A:387, GLU A:86, ASP A:385

Resveratrol	-7.8	LYS A:75, LEU A:130, PRO A:111, ILE A:384, ASP A:385, ILE A:65, ASP A:132, THR A:134
Myricetin	-7.2	GLU A:194, ASN A:195, GLY A:180, LEU A:179, GLN A:196, MET A 181, VAL A: 133, ASP A: 132, THR A: 134, VAL A: 73

Mol 7(Fisetin) and Mol 12(Resveratrol) were found to be having higher binding energies with the protein 6m89 than our cocrystal ligand Quercetin.

6.3 Visualization of docked complex and its binding pattern of ligand

Figure 5: (a) 2D visualization of binding interaction of co-crystal ligand (mol 1); (b) best binding mode with protein

Figure 6: (c) 2D visualization of binding interaction of mol 7; (d) best binding mode with protein for mol 7

Figure 7: (e) 2D visualization of binding interaction of mol 12; (f) Best binding mode with protein for mol 12

7. CONCLUSION

The most promising reports concerning anti-aging effects of Quercetin are revealed through the molecular docking studies by suggesting that quercetin influences multiple signaling pathways, such as activation of sirtuins, AMPK, and Nrf2. This research report supply the structural features of the molecular mechanisms of the therapeutic efficacy of quercetin in preventing aging. It as well explains its efficacy and safety. Quercetin-derived approaches Strongly represents an emerging solution for the preservation of optimum life span and warding off age-related diseases. The use of phenolic extracts emerges as a viable alternative for cosmetic application, ensuring a commitment to sustainability. However, it is of crucial importance to evaluate the toxicity risks of raw materials and finished products.

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9. APPENDIX

❖ List of abbreviations

- * (ADMET) Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Elimination & Toxicity
- * (admetSAR) Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Elimination & Toxicity Structure Activity Relationship
- * (CRP) C-reactive Protein
- * (CID) Compound Identity Number
- * (OPLS3) Optimized Potentials for Liquid Simulations 3
- * (RCSB) Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics
- * (PDB) Protein Data Bank
- * (pH) Potential of Hydrogen
- * (EGCG) Epigallocatechin gallate